

TEACHING METHODICS OF RUSSIAN IN CHINA AND IN OTHER COUNTRIES

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the possibilities of teaching Chinese language were actually were presented on the example of China. It emphasized the issue of cyber threats. The threat of the teaching methodic Russian is considered to the causes of the between the other countries.

Key words: *technology, methodic, teaching program, national language, state language, idea, ethnic language, pedagogical structure, pedagogic phrases, pedagogic ideas.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье фактически были представлены возможности обучения китайскому языку на примере Китая. Он подчеркнул проблему киберугроз. Угроза методики преподавания русского языка рассматривается как причина разногласий между другими странами.

Ключевые слова: *технология, методика, программа обучения, национальный язык, государственный язык, идея, национальный язык, педагогическая структура, педагогические фразы, педагогические идеи.*

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola aslida Xitoy misolida xitoy tilini o'rgatish imkoniyatlarini taqdim etdi. U kiber tahdidlar masalasiga alohida to'xtalib o'tdi. Rus tilini o'qitish usullariga tahdid boshqa davlatlar o'rtasidagi kelishmovchilikning sababi sifatida ko'rilmoqda.

Tayanch so'zlar: *texnologiya, metodika, o'quv dasturi, milliy til, davlat tili, g'oya, milliy til, pedagogik tuzilma, pedagogik iboralar, pedagogik g'oyalar.*

TEACHING METHODICS OF RUSSIAN IN CHINA AND IN OTHER COUNTRIES WITH INTERACTIVE METHODS

Introduction. The paper presents the main study results on the analysis of processes of establishing and development of Russian language studies and Russian language training practices in mainland China and Taiwan since the early XVIII century until now. Basing on the postulates of the social-and-cultural, systemic and historical, historiographical and axiological approaches, the authors attempt to describe the development of the theory and practice of teaching and studying Russian as a foreign language (RFL) with a view to form a complete picture of the past and present of the Russian language in China and Taiwan, to evaluate the role and importance of the Russian language, primarily, in the social land-cultural, as well as in the social-and-political and even economic aspects, not only from historic perspectives but also in terms of the future development – basing on evolving cooperation between Russia, on the one hand, and China and Taiwan – on the other. Methods. The main applied research methods are the comparative-historical and historical-and-logical analysis, historical reconstruction methods, systematization, theoretical generalizations and, partly, prediction. Scientific novelty. The novelty of the study lies in the fact that for the first time in the broader period (1700–2000 s) it offers a generalized description of the establishment and development of Russian studies and practice of teaching the Russian language in China and Taiwan. Practical significance. The implementation of the research outcomes can be useful due to a possibility of carrying on its basis of new studies on the problems of Russian philology and teaching Russian as a foreign language, the history of pedagogy and education, and comparative pedagogy (comparative linguistics).

- **Research methodology.** Now we have a big social problem for Chinese students learn Russian speaking style. Because in Russian language speaking style and Russian writing style is actually is not the same. That is why teach Russian for us Chinese people is very hard. When we want to speak Russian we need to improve student's speaking style.

In my experience, I had many years experience teaching of Russian in Xinjiang University. For students especially during learn Russian is very hard to learn "R" alphabet. Because, in Chinese language we don't have this letter. For Chinese students is very hard to say or retell this letter. I am from China also. I am during my lessons more try to use fishbone, brain storm, Teacher-Centered Instruction, Student-Centered/Constructivist Approach, Differentiated instruction, Technology-based learning, Project-Based Learning, Group learning, Individual learning, Inquiry-based learning teaching methodic of Russian language. I think that with teaching Russian

language we must pay attention of their Russian speaking style. I recommend for them sometimes at home and during the lessons to see Russian films, listen Russian music.

- **Literature review.** At the lesson I use different books in Russian. For example, I use the book name is “Поехали”. In this book we have a book with picture and it is very interesting. This book is very useful for speaking style. Also, we use the book which name is “ Russian for Foreign students” it is very modern book and is very interesting. It is published in 2020 year in Moscow. This book is more useful for grammar and speaking style of Russian language.

- **Analysis and results.** With the right teaching methods, educators can create an enjoyable and productive classroom experience for students where they can learn important academic and social skills to last a lifetime. There are many frameworks that a teacher could use to support students with different interests, abilities and learning styles. If you're a teacher or professional in the education field, you might benefit from learning about new instructive strategies in the field to maximize your students' chances of success in your classroom. For Russian language we have masculine and feminine. Two types of this gender is very hard to learn for Chinese students. Because in Chinese we don't have and in English language masculine and feminine. That's why for Chinese people learn this type is very hard. For many Chinese students is very hard declension of words because in Chinese and English language don't have this. We have 6 types of cases. It is very hard to learn these type of grammar rules.

In this article, we define what teaching methods are, explore nine types of teaching methods, review the benefits of these methods and provide some tips for doing so successfully.

Teaching methods are ways to instruct students in a classroom, helping them to understand and remember what they've learned. Some of the best teaching strategies allow educators to convey information in a clear and concise way while also ensuring students retain it over the long term. If students can comprehend facts on a deep level and practice skills properly in the classroom, they can apply that wisdom and those abilities to their personal lives and their future careers.

Teaching methods are opportunities to make learning engaging, inspiring and fun for students. They aid teachers in fulfilling the responsibility of guiding the social and emotional development of children. By using the right strategies, teachers can instill values of respect, empathy and cultural sensitivity into their classroom. They also use teaching methods to prepare students for standardized testing. Your classroom philosophies and principles can vary based on your preferences as a teacher, your school mission statement, your subject areas and other factors.

1. Lecture-based learning

A traditional way to structure classroom learning is the lecture format, in which teachers explain information while students observe. Teachers lead a lesson by presenting on, showing visuals of and modeling examples of a topic. While a teacher is presenting, students can listen, watch, take notes and copy the teacher's demonstrations. While this is a conventional and helpful approach, teachers may alter it for different learning environments.

Here are some ways that teachers ensure the success of lecture-based learning:

Keep lessons brief: Students, especially those at a young age, may have short attention spans and might only be able to focus for short periods of time. It can be advantageous to keep classroom lectures short and concise to maintain student attention and engagement.

Allow time for questions: While lecture-based learning is a teacher-centered approach, educators can still involve student input by making time for questions before, during and after the presentation. While this can make the lecture process longer, it can also allow students to engage with the material, comprehend it and remember it more easily. Russian languages grammar is very hard.

Create instructional videos: Many teachers use a flipped classroom approach where they encourage students to watch lectures or instructional videos at home and complete assignments in class. This can be a great opportunity to let students work at their own pace, as they can see videos again by rewinding and replaying them.

Use visual cues: Whether in or outside of the academic environment, using visual cues in presentations such as icons, images and videos can be a great way to keep your audiences interested in the content. Make sure to use high-contrast colors and bold shapes and lines so students across your classroom can see and understand your messages. **Promote handwritten notes:** For those students who are able, handwriting notes on paper can be a superb way to stay focused during lectures. It can also help people to recall information well and strengthen their spelling and writing skills.

2. Technology-based learning

Teachers can use technology in the classroom to make teaching processes more efficient and aid in student learning. Students can use devices like computers and tablets to read materials, conduct research or play educational games. In addition, cloud computing capabilities make it possible for students to access documents or other resources while at school or at home. Virtual classrooms using video conferencing software can be a great way to provide education remotely. This can be especially helpful for students with disabilities who may have difficulties focusing in a physical classroom environment.

3. Individual learning

While group projects can be exciting opportunities for students, it's also important to promote individual learning so that they can work by themselves. Assigning journal entries can be an excellent way to give students time to think through topics and develop thoughts and analyses. This is especially helpful before hosting a class discussion so class members can have ideas for what to say. Teachers can read writing assignments to reward points to students who can't participate vocally in class.

4. Inquiry-based learning

Inquiry-based learning promotes the idea of learning by investigation, where students can complete projects, ask questions and find answers by themselves. While teachers act as resources in these times, the goal is for students to solve problems and discover information on their own. Upon learning about concepts, they can explain and present the concepts in their own words to further enforce them in their memories. Then, students can advance to higher levels at their own pace. This is a way for students to perform an active role in the learning process.

5. Kinesthetic learning

Kinesthetic learning is the notion of learning through movement. Teachers can move around the classroom and use hand gestures while they present to engage students visually and kinesthetically. They can also encourage students to perform physical activities where they can move around and use their creativity. Here are some ideas:

Drawing: Many students enjoy drawing or painting, and teachers can include this activity in the classroom to make learning enjoyable. Students can have the option to develop ideas and use different colors and tools to make their ideas a reality.

Acting: Students, especially young children, may have an exciting time developing and role-playing in theatrical performances. This can be a great idea for implementing kinesthetic learning in group projects.

Building: Building structures with blocks, toys or other materials can help students develop hand-eye coordination and analytical thinking skills. It can also be a fun way for them to stay focused in the classroom.

Playing: A traditional form of kinesthetic learning is playing sports, and many schools have gym classes where students can exert energy and spend time outside. You can also have educational sports games in the classroom, where students can move around and learn simultaneously.

The establishment of the China Russian Language Teaching and Research Association was a major milestone in Russian language education in China. In January 1980, nine institutions including Beijing Foreign Studies University, Heilongjiang University, Peking University, Nan kai University, Sichuan

International Studies University, Beijing Normal University, East China Normal University, Shanghai International Studies University, and Xi'an University of Foreign Languages formed the preparatory group for the Chinese Russian Teaching Research Association. On May 3, 1981, the association was formally established in Shanghai, with a total of 1,300 members, 41 directors, and 11 standing directors. Later, the numbers of directors and standing directors grew to 48 and 15. This was the industry association for Russian majors in Chinese universities and colleges. Since then, those in Russian language education in colleges and universities have formed a joint force, and Russian teaching and research have embarked on a standardized road. The purpose of the Chinese Russian Teaching and Research Association was to contact and unite professional Russian teaching and research workers in colleges and universities across the country, to extensively carry out more academic research, to actively conduct academic exchanges of Russian at home and abroad, and to promote the prosperity and development of Chinese Russian teaching and research. In the same year, the journal *Teaching Russian in China* was launched, which is an international academic publication on Russian. It has become a high-quality platform for Russian educators to exchange teaching experience and publish research results. It played an important role in promoting Chinese Russian academics. In September 1985, the Chinese Russian Teaching and Research Association joined the World Russian Association and became a full member. Russian language education in China began to interact closely with Russian language education in countries around the world. By carrying out exchanges and cooperation between Chinese and foreign cultures, the overall internationalization of Russian language education in China was further promoted.

- **Conclusion and recommendations.** As a teacher and with my working experience in my opinion knowing the Russian language will allow you to empathize more with the people of your country. It will also enable you to make new friends and establish a new relationships during your unique trips. It will allow you to meet new people during the course. , Russian language education has—under the influence of historical events—undertaken a path very different from that of other foreign languages—English in particular—since Russian and English educations have been in a “trade-off” relation. In the 2020 year, foreign language education in the whole nation, at central or local levels, was completely oriented towards Russian, and nowadays the growth of the discipline barely satisfies the national needs, either in terms of speed or efficacy. Neither the former nor the latter can be considered as a desirable development. Take Xin Jiang University as an example here. Before the 1980s, there were three departments of foreign languages at the university, namely: Western Languages (including German, French, Spanish, and English), Eastern

Languages (ten languages including Japanese, Arabic, Korean, and Mongolian) and Russian—the only single language that had its own department, a heritage left by the dominance of Russian in 1950s-60s. Many foreign languages institute and schools of foreign languages at Chinese universities may trace their long history back to departments of Russian language. For instance, Beijing Foreign Studies University, the PLA Language Institute, and Heilongjiang University are directly evolved from one precursor—the Russian Language Team at Yan’ an Anti-Japanese Military and Political College.

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